

THE IMPORTANT ASPECTS OF THE LABOR COMPENSATION SYSTEM

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Annotation: The article is devoted to open significant points connected to the aspects of labor compensation for today, its main function in economics and types. On the other hand key factors affecting compensation management are highlighted.

Key words: *classical economics, neoclassical economics, mental effort, homogeneous input, Competitive compensation, Compensation management, Labour unions, direct compensation, indirect compensation.*

In classical economics, labor is one of the three factors of production, along with land and capital. Labor is often defined as the physical or mental effort exerted by human beings in the production of goods and services. In neoclassical economics, labor is a broader concept that incorporates all human activity that adds value to a product or service. This includes not only physical and mental effort but also the use of tools, machines, and other equipment. It also surrounds the time spent on planning, organizing, and supervising production. In certain economic models, labor is assumed to be a homogeneous input. This means that all workers are assumed to have the same skills, abilities, and productivity. However, labor is not homogeneous in real life. Workers differ in their skills, abilities, experience, and motivation.

Compensation has always been one of the main reasons employees change jobs, and, while other factors are certainly contributing to an increase in turnover

these days, compensation, including salaries and benefits, is still the [main driver](#) of turnover. Worker compensation systems (WCS) are usually part of the social benefit or social security schemes of the EU Member States. The purposes of the different WCS are always the same. They were introduced to establish a system which insures workers against the impairment of work-related injuries and, at the same time, relieves the employers from their financial liability. In this way WCS contribute substantially to social peace and stable markets. However, the details of each WCS are different with regard to organisation, funding, coverage and membership. Principally there are two traditional schemes for social security and for worker compensation. A detailed description of different schemes and compensation systems can be found in the OSH Wiki Article ‘International comparison of occupations accident insurance systems’.

The Bismarckian scheme, named after Otto von Bismarck, the chancellor of the German Reich who introduced the first social insurance scheme in the 1880s. Bismarckian social insurance is mainly financed by contributions from its members. In the case of worker compensation the members are the companies (employers).

The Beveridgean scheme, named after William Henry Beveridge, who issued a ground-breaking report on “Social Insurance and Allied Services” to the British Parliament in 1942. In practice, the social insurance schemes in EU Members States following the Beveridgean tradition are mainly tax financed.

The models can also be clustered by considering cultural heritage and the political nature of the welfare system: In this way we can distinguish between three (or four) models, those being the Anglo-Saxon (market oriented) welfare state, the Central European (Bismarckian) welfare state, the Scandinavian (social-democratic) welfare state, and the Mediterranean / Eastern European models, which are either described as hybrid (combining attributes of the first three) or as still developing systems.

As EU-OSHA stated in its report [1], some EU Member States combine elements of the two basic models. Furthermore, cultural and societal elements play a decisive role. Moreover, within each of the two general schemes, insurance for occupational accidents and diseases can be offered by public (monopolistic) institutions or by private (market oriented) providers [2]. The competitiveness of the current job market has given workers more leverage when it comes to pay and benefits. Leaders considering whether or not they can and will meet the demands of workers should be aware of just how important compensation is to holding onto talented employees. Compensation is important for employee retention because it helps companies avoid the high costs associated with turnover. Competitive compensation packages also help organizations attract and keep top talent and can lead to greater employee satisfaction, making it more likely employees will stay.

Compensation management is one of the primary functions of HR, as it plays a crucial role in attracting and retaining top talent. It is managing and determining an employer's compensation to the employees in return for their work. Compensation management involves managing, analysing, and determining the salary, benefits, and incentives paid to the employees. Compensation management plays a crucial role in attracting and retaining top talent. It includes monetary as well as non-monetary benefits. It also increases employee productivity and reduces employee turnover. Additionally, it ensures that every employee gets paid a fair wage based on industry standards, work experience, company budget, etc. Key factors affecting compensation management are given below:

- Productivity of workers
 - Ability to pay
- Government policies
 - Labour unions
 - Cost of living

- Demand and supply of labour
 - Industry standards
1. Productivity of workers– Productivity-based compensation helps derive the best results. The higher the productivity of employees, the more should be the compensation.
 2. Ability to pay– If your company has high profitability, you can pay better compensation and [retain your employees](#) and vice versa.
 3. Government Policies– Government also has certain policies to protect employee interests. The employer has to pay the employees as per governmental regulations and provide benefits such as PF, medical insurance, [gratuity](#), and pension.
 4. Labour Unions– They also play an essential role in ensuring employees get a fair wage. They fight with the employers for the employee’s rights and wage revision.
 5. Cost of Living– Cost of living also influences compensation to a large extent. An employee based in a city with a high cost of living needs a higher salary and vice versa.
 6. Demand and Supply of Labour– It is one of the most important factors that affect the compensation of employees. If the demand is more than the supply, the compensation will be higher.
 7. Industry Standards– No employee would like to join a company whose compensation is below the industry standards. Therefore you need to analyse the standard market rates of different roles and pay your employees accordingly. The types of compensation are broadly classified into direct compensation and indirect compensation.

The types of compensation are broadly classified into direct compensation and indirect compensation. Direct Compensation- it is the monetary benefits provided by the employer to the employees.

- ✓ Hourly pay– Hourly pay is the salary paid for each hour of work that the employee does.
- ✓ Salary– Salary is the fixed monthly amount that the employer pays to the employee in cash.
- ✓ Commission– A monetary reward that is paid based on the performance of an individual. It is generally provided in the case of sales jobs as a fixed percentage.
- ✓ Bonus– A bonus is a monetary incentive paid to employees for their good performance. It is paid over and above the employee’s basic salary.

Indirect Compensation- indirect compensation refers to non-monetary benefits like paid holidays, insurance, and retirement benefits.

- ✓ Insurance– Employers generally provide employees with medical insurance to ensure good health of their employees. If you are an early-stage startup facing difficulties getting employee insurance, check out [RazorpayX Payroll](#). It provides group insurance packages to teams as small as 2!
- ✓ Paid holidays– Paid holidays are provided to help employees maintain a work-life balance.
- ✓ ESOPs– Sometimes, companies also provide their employees with their shares at a discounted price, offering them an additional opportunity to earn.
- ✓ Retirement Benefits– Retirement benefits include gratuity, pension, general provident fund, [leave encashment](#), etc.

Leave travel allowance– LTA or leave travel allowance is the non-monetary benefit provided by the employer to the employee where the employer covers the employee’s travel expenses[3].

- ✓ Relocation expenses– Relocation expenses are the benefits the employer provides in case the job requires relocation to a different city.

- ✓ While the list of reasons why you should focus on compensation management is rather long, here are a few main reasons:
- ✓ Helps Plan Your Budget– Employee salaries are the highest cost for any startup. Compensation management helps determine the costs beforehand and plan the budget accordingly. It also helps plan increments and other benefits based on industry standards.
- ✓ Helps Motivate Employees- Compensation is the key factor influencing an employee’s productivity. A well-paid employee is more likely to work hard for your company and vice versa.
- ✓ Reduces Employee Turnover– Giving adequate monetary and non-monetary benefits helps increase job satisfaction and reduce the rate of employee turnover.
- ✓ Attracts Best Talent– it not only prevents employees from switching jobs but also helps attract top talent. The best talent always looks for a company with a competitive salary and benefits like insurance, paid time off, leave allowance, [flexible benefits](#), etc. The huge number of employees makes manual compensation management tiresome and error-prone. The best way to deal with the payroll of a huge number of employees is to use payroll processing software like [RazorpayX Payroll](#).

All in all, we should note that work is important not only because of the wage connected with it. Work itself is important. Without work for a long time, people can go crazy. We are workers by nature. If we do not occupy ourselves, we suffer as persons. Work gives us dignity. It gives us energy. It gives us meaning. Those who have much responsibilities complain of too much work. Their dream is to be totally free from work. However, we should be forewarned. If this indeed happens, and we have been given a taste of it due to the prolonged lack down, we suffer much more. It is not heavenly to be sleeping the whole day, or to watch one movie after another for days, or to be glued to video games every day[4]. This is

not life! The quarantine has also brought out clearly the importance of labor in our economy. The virus does not affect capital – the machineries, the materials, the money in the bank – they are intact. But capital is useless without labor. Everything comes to a halt because there are no workers to make the factories run, to man the businesses, to work in the offices. So, capital remains dead, useless. This is why we say that there is priority of labor over capital. Labor is more important than capital. In fact it is the work of human beings that makes capital grow. By itself capital is stagnant!

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